

ANALYSIS OF REFINERY'S STEAM NETWORK OPERATION

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Abstract

The steam network and its mass balance in a refinery evolve along the commissioning of the new and decommissioning of obsolete production units. The share of steam produced in local steam sources on total steam consumption in SLOVNAFT refinery steadily increases, both due to improved residual heat utilization and implemented steam saving measures. As a result, risk of cold spots occurrence in steam mains, leading to extensive steam condensation in pipelines and the risk of water hammer increased. Other spots in pipelines on the other hand suffer from high steam velocities, accompanied with increased steam pressure losses. Both operational states are unwelcome when striving towards stable and efficient steam network operation. The presented contribution tackles the above problem by means of analysis of current operational state including that of the individual production units steam balance. The present operational state of the steam network is depicted, along with the work already performed in the past aimed at its operation stabilization. Troublesome spots in the network are highlighted and the reasons for their occurrence are elucidated. Steam balance calculation results on all three steam pressure levels indicate both significant steam losses in the grid as well as the existence of several unreliable local steam consumption measurements. Proposals for their detailed check are formulated, striving to improve the quality of available steam network operation process data in the future that should in turn allow for more reliable prediction of future steam network balance and topology changes on delivered steam quality and steam network management comfort.

Introduction

Water steam is undeniably one of the most extensively used energetic media ever. Already in the 2006 the share of energy consumption in the form of water steam represented up to 40 % of all energetic media used in industry. Especially in oil industry up to 28 % of total energy consumption belongs to water steam production¹. Instead of many decentralized water steam sources, the system of central steam source is preferred, with steam transport from single central source to its consumers through complicated pipe networks with total length reaching up few tens to hundreds kilometers within one plant. While operational state being influenced by large number of parameters, it is difficult to keep it in stable state and secure desired steam quality under all conditions. In addition to it, the oil refinery acts like living, dynamic system, whose operational state is constantly changing and evolving. Steam networks consist of an immense number of structural elements and fittings of different species and shapes. Inevitable components of each steam network are condensate drains. Their role is to let off the redundant air during production startup and to drain the condensed steam during ordinary production state in effort to minimize water steam losses. Practical experiences confirm that condensate drains are often not working optimally and are responsible for considerable steam losses. In case of improper condensate drain operation or their improper layout, increased amount of condensate in pipes may appear. At higher velocities (typically 20 m/s and higher), the effect of water hammer may appear. Proposed work does not deal with condensate drains, their design and maintenance, however takes a look from the opposite side – how to improve steam network stability, which may lead to avoiding increased condensation risk.

As in other cases, it is desired to keep steam networks in stable state because of unfavourable effects of often fluctuations to production units in refinery. Stable and effective operation of steam networks also means reducing steam losses to environment. Application of mathematical models on different problems within oil industry or other branches in order to optimize water steam operation is common. A very simple mathematical model based only on mass and heat balance, which enabled switching between different production loads and switching between electro- and steam drive, found practical use in oil refinery. It helped to solve problem of „cold spots“ formation and positive results of tests of changes impact lead to realisation of new projects in steam network². Few measures designed based on their results were realised and the steam network in this state with little adjustments is working to this day. Luo et. al. in his work proposed relatively simple mathematical model and refer to previous models of other authors. Steam flow velocity in each pipe segment can be more precisely

determined only by combination hydrodynamical equations and heat balance³. Tian applied laws of mass, momentum and energy conservation to solve steam flow equations⁴. Nonlinear and complex character of hydraulic-heat model of steam networks causes typically iterative calculations with great extent. Luo et. al. created a mathematical model solving steam flow velocities calculations in each pipe independently. As each mathematical model, it adopts certain simplifications, which on the other hand seem to be accomplished at real operational state. The principle of this mathematical model is based on solving matrixes, whose dimensions depend on number of pipes and nodes. By analysing the steam pipe network model, one can find the key to the problem is the unknown intermediate nodes' temperature and pressure values, which don't represent any steam producer or steam consumer. The method to obtain these values is described in their work precisely. Comparison of calculated and experimental values showed maximal relative error of no more than 6 %. It is possible to use this mathematical model for steam network simulation, measured data diagnostics or steam network design and innovation. However, in case of unbalanced system, alternative solutions need to be found. More sophisticated mathematical models manage to handle a multiphase flow. Mathematical model predicting the amount of condensate and considering condensate losses was proposed in the past and allows application on single pipes or whole steam networks^{4,5}. It consists of differential equations based on mass and energy conservation laws. Heat losses are divided into latent heat, which causes only temperature drop, and sensible heat, which is responsible for condensate production. Based on this concept, a proportionality coefficient, which indicates a part of heat losses belonging to steam condensation, was defined. This seems to be the key parameter for condensation amount calculation by this mathematical model. Values obtained by this mathematical model were compared with those obtained by models of other authors as well as experimental ones. When applied to a single pipe, practically only small differences in the condensate amount were observed. In case of whole network in a large Chinese steel plant, very good results were obtained. Relative errors for mass flow, pressure and temperature calculations of 1.99 %, 1.97 % and 2.2 % respectively were calculated under winter conditions. In summer, mass flow calculation error changed to -4.57 % while the others remained the same.

The current trend in the field of hydrodynamics is an effort to solve complicated systems by CFD modelling, which is based on solving the Navier-Stokes equation and is being used by many commercially available softwares like ANSYS Fluent, SimFlow, etc. This is possible especially thanks to a rapid computational technics development.

Simulation

The effectivity of steam network operation can be reviewed by carrying out its mass and heat balance. In SLOVNAFT refinery, water steam in three pressure levels is used. Steam networks of all pressure levels are connected to each other, which allows the steam of higher pressure to be favourably let down to lower pressure level (HPS to MPS or LPS, MPS to LPS). However, each pressure level steam network was balanced separately. Mass and heat balances as well as flow velocity calculations were done by simple balance model in MS Excel. Current operational state balance is based on measured operational data, but occasional operational unit shutdowns, measuring failures or missing measuring instruments make it difficult to provide a reliable set of data. The data preparation itself was not a simple task and required increased attention because of large extent of data, which should create a base for simulation thus reviewing the steam network operational state. To avoid results distortion, a maximal effort for accuracy and data completeness should be taken. The input parameters for this mathematical model were steam mass flows, temperatures and pressures measured on each operational unit. Calculation schemes were completed on the base of real steam network plans and inspections in SLOVNAFT refinery with emphasis on topology conservation and part of HPS calculation scheme is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A segment of HPS simulation scheme for balance model of steam networks

Prior to simulation, obsolete operational units or non-productional units with negligible steam consumption were sorted out. Dimensions of each pipe segments were the next input parameters for this mathematical model, which allowed the calculations of steam flow velocities inside the pipes. Simultaneously with Balance model, another Hydrodynamical model in commercially available software was developed. This tool enables to choose one of many flow calculation correlations, while the Beggs & Brill correlation, which is a primary correlation used by this software and provides standard for similar calculations⁶, was used. The input parameters for Hydrodynamical model were the same as those for Balance model – steam mass flows, temperatures, pressures and dimensions of each pipe segments. Unlike simple Balance model, this one is much more complex and can easily perform hydrodynamical calculations as well as heat loss calculations. Thus, the next input parameters for this model are thermal insulation thickness and heat conductivity, weather conditions as outside temperature or wind speed. For hydrodynamical equations, parameters as construction material, length and diameter or height elevation of each segment, fittings number, sorts and dimensions were important.

Output from the Balance model are differences between total mass of produced and consumed steam and total heat produced and consumed in the form of steam (Figure 2), respectively, as well as steam flow velocities in each pipe segment (Figure 3). Output from the Hydrodynamical model are steam flows, temperatures and pressures at each steam consuming unit. The goal is to, based on results obtained by mathematical models, review the total operational state of steam network, detect troublesome spots in pipelines and detect different possibilities for operational stability improvement thus leading to operational costs reduction and some technological problems elimination. Since the values for output streams in the case of Hydrodynamical model are calculated, measured and calculated steam mass flows, temperatures and pressures at steam consuming units can be compared. Simulation by hydrodynamical model was performed with the data recorded on the 22.4.2017 at 6:00. Decision after previous inspection of the steam networks' state and consultation with responsible staff led to simulation with 1 condensate drain and 4 rectangular knees situated once every 100 m. Heat losses were calculated for standard thermal insulation thickness used in SLOVNAFT refinery ($\delta_i=120$ mm), its thermal conductivity $\lambda=0.038$ Wm⁻¹K⁻¹ and ambient temperature set according to hydrometeorological records at this day.

Mathematical modelling is an excellent tool in case of planned measures, which allows the steam networks reviewing or potential troublesome spots detecting. Based on these results, one can decide whether the solution is favourable or not and propose changes to secure the most satisfying operational state. The advantage of both mathematical models proposed in this work is their simple modifiability and ability to simulate different variations of calculation schemes with ease. In addition, the Hydrodynamical model offers satisfactory accuracy of heat losses and pressure drop in pipes calculations.

Results and discussion

During the period from 1.1.2017 to 31.12.2017 HPS network in SLOVNAFT refinery was analysed. A total of 8760 data sets, each consisting of 78 weighted hour average values of independent measurements of process variables, were processed. The Balance model showed, that average difference between the amounts of produced and consumed steam in HPS network is 9.37 t/h, which is 25.32 % of the amount supplied by CHP unit or 9.87 % of total steam volume distributed in HPS network. Results of mass balance are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Results of mass balance of the HPS network

Figure 3. Results of heat balance of the HPS network

As expected, results of heat balance show similar trend as mass balance and they are shown in Figure 3. However, few differences can be observed, which may be caused by estimation of specific enthalpy of steam when data are not available. Average heat losses of 35.93 GJ/h are 26.66 % of the heat imported from CHP unit or 12.31 % of total heat supply in HPS network. Subtracting the results of heat and mass balance, one gets the

average value of specific enthalpy of steam. Obtained value of 3.84 MJ/t is inadequate, because the enthalpy of HPS is typically between 2.8 and 3.1 MJ/t. Since heat flow is directly proportional to mass flow, one can conclude, that the inconsistency arises due to incorrect temperature, pressure or both measurements.

Figure 4. HPS flow velocity history at unit S2

Mass and heat balance results attract attention due to occasional negative values, which means higher steam consumption than its production in HPS network. There raises a question – how is it possible? This effect could be partially caused by inaccuracy of some measuring instruments, but this would result in a systematic error during whole period evaluated. Another explanation could be a slow system dynamics. In case of immediate steam consumption increase at certain production unit, the CHP plant may not provide a reaction fast enough and slow dynamics causes extended time needed to CHP being able to deliver desired amount of steam. However, this is not a problem in SLOVNAFT refinery.

In terms of steam flow velocity, pipe segments between individual production units were analysed and flow velocity was calculated based on steam mass flows, specific volumes and pipe segments diameters. Literature often deals with maximal steam flow velocities in pipes. Flow velocities in case of saturated steam should not exceed 30 to 40 m/s, says Spirax Sarco company, the world excellence in steam system engineering⁷. However, this information should be taken with care, because individual situations depending on the water steam state, the number of fittings and the pipe segments lengths may occur. In intentions of proposed work, a limit for flow velocity of value 30 m/s was considered for the simple reason. On 11.7.2017, operating problems at S2 unit were reported by its workers. HPS produced at this unit could not be transported into steam network and operational pressure had to be increased up to the upper limit value. S2 unit is situated at the end of pipeline at least 300 m away from previous operation unit, which is also acts as a steam producer. What's worse, the steam produced at S2 unit is close to its saturation point. Calculations at this certain time confirmed the flow velocity value slightly over 30 m/s at this pipe segment as can be seen in Figure 4. At these conditions, there is a risk of condensate formation in the pipeline.

Calculated values of pressure corresponded very well to the experimental ones and average relative error of only 2.70 %. It must be highlighted, that such accurate results were obtained also thanks to correct estimation of hydraulic resistances in the form of knees and condensate drains. Visual inspection also proved non-ideal state of thermal insulation caused by weather conditions and advanced steam networks' age. Technical state is worse and the insulation is deformed or missing. Following simulations were thus performed with higher value of insulation's thermal conductivity $\lambda=0.08 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ based on manufacturer's informations⁸, which led to higher value of heat losses. After results analysis a conclusion was formulated. Average relative error for temperature of 9.73 % shows, that the technical state of thermal insulation is most likely much worse. Differences between calculated and experimental temperature values at certain operation units reached up to 35 °C. Higher differences on the other hand may be caused by incorrect temperature measurement, which is highly

frequented phenomenon in practice. Results of simulation were compared with experimental values and are shown in Table I together with differences and relative errors.

Table I
Comparison of experimental and calculated values of temperature and pressure

Unit	T _{exp} [°C]	T _{calc} [°C]	ΔT [°C]	δ _T [%]	P _{exp} [MPa(g)]	P _{calc} [MPa(g)]	ΔP _{exp} [MPa]	δ _P [%]
CHP	300.67	315.20	-14.53	-4.83	3.16	3.1	0.06	1.90
C1	331.43	359.00	-27.57	-8.32	3.17	3.20	-0.03	-0.99
C2'	313.40	349.70	-36.30	-11.58	-	3.20	-	-
C2	358.26	362.10	-3.84	-1.07	3.24	3.21	0.03	0.89
C3	326.98	349.70	-22.72	-6.95	2.88	3.20	-0.32	-11.17
C4	251.71	294.10	-42.39	-16.84	3.31	3.13	0.18	5.28
C5	295.19	303.50	-8.31	-2.82	3.31	3.13	0.18	5.28
C6	300.74	330.00	-29.26	-9.73	3.24	3.23	0.01	0.42
C7	335.71	336.20	-0.49	-0.15	3.18	3.12	0.06	2.06
C8	324.16	328.10	-3.94	-1.22	3.18	3.13	0.05	1.81
C9	335.71	319.60	16.11	4.80	3.18	3.13	0.05	1.78
C11	242.33	252.70	-10.37	-4.28	3.11	3.16	-0.05	-1.76
C12	272.59	336.00	-63.41	-23.26	-	3.16	-	-
C13	254.02	342.20	-88.18	-34.72	3.11	3.15	-0.04	-1.23

Conclusions

Proposed work deals with analysis of present HPS networks operational state and simulation done by two mathematical models in order to identify troublesome spots and probably inaccurate operational measuring instruments in SLOVNAFT refinery. The Balance model provides look at the steam network as a whole and offers results in the form of difference between the amount of produced and consumed steam in the steam network. This method can be applied to the analysis and assessment of steam network operational state throughout the year. This model is capable of steam flow velocity calculations in individual pipe segments, however results need to be taken with care in the case of unbalanced system. Potential cold spots or bottlenecks (as in the case of unit S2) can be identified this way.

The Hydrodynamical model offers very accurate pressure drop in pipe calculations in connection with heat losses amount calculations. Based on results obtained by this model, one can conclude, that pressure measurements are performed correctly and values correspond very well. In terms of temperatures, conclusions about bad thermal insulation state at HPS network were made, because of differences between calculated and experimental values of few tens centigrade. Results of both mathematical models indicate possible problems with temperature measurement and few suspicious measurement instruments were selected for control. In near future, the SLOVNAFT refinery plans to check them and replace if necessary.

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